

DELIVERABLE

D2.1.1 LIST OF THE RELEVANT INDICATORS FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF CONSCIOUSNESS OF BROILERS AND TURKEYS AFTER WATERBATH STUNNING

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1. Introduction

1.1. Activity 2. Animal welfare indicators, methods for the assessment and methods of improvement

Article 21 (8) (e) of Regulation **(EU) 2017/625** states that “the Commission shall lay down rules on the cases and conditions where official controls to verify compliance with animal welfare requirements may include the use of specific animal welfare indicators based on measurable performance criteria, and the design of such indicators on the basis of scientific and technical evidence”. The European Union Reference Centre for animal welfare for poultry and other small farmed animals should provide scientific and technological expertise for the development and application of the animal welfare indicators referred to in point (e) of **Article 21(8)** and **Article 96 (b)** and developing or coordinating the development of methods for the assessments of the level of welfare of animals and of methods for the improvement of the welfare of animals (**Article 96 (c)**).

1.2. Sub-activity 2.1: Relevant animal welfare indicators

The set of deliverable is part of the sub-activity 2.1 “relevant animal welfare indicators”, which aims to list the poultry welfare indicators regarding the three priority area:

Priority 1. Broilers welfare on farm.

Priority 2. Laying hens welfare in alternative housing systems.

Priority 3. State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys.

*This deliverable focuses only on: **Priority 3. State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys.***

The set of deliverable will be followed up with future output of the same sub-activity, such as the description of the considered validated indicators among the identified ones and associated methodology and the identification of gaps of knowledge regarding missing/not validated indicators and prioritisation of the future topics to work on during the next period. This deliverable is also the base for sub-activity 2.2 to identify the legal requirements which are more difficult to implement and to propose better indicators and methods of animal welfare assessment. Furthermore, it will help in in sub-activity 3.1 to identify the gaps of knowledge regarding indicators to check legal requirements and formulate different topics for scientific and technical studies.

This set of deliverable identifies the legal requirements of the legislation and addresses their corresponding specific indicators for each requirement, classified as animal-based, resource-based and management-based indicators. The indicators have been retrieved from literature review and expert knowledge. Furthermore, the legal requirements without specific corresponding indicators have been identified. The search of missing specific indicators in national guidance and the assessment of validity of the

key indicators identified here will be reviewed in the next deliverables (deliverables **D.2.1.2** and **D.2.1.3**). Furthermore, a description of improved methods for the assessment of welfare will be provided (deliverable **D.2.2.2**). This document is only delivering the indicators that can be directly linked with a specific legal requirement. Broader indicators on animal welfare for each priority area will be delivered in the next working period under the denomination “iceberg indicators”.

Definition and examples of the terminology used:

Legal requirement: a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls.

Example: Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 3, Paragraph 1: *“Animals shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress or suffering during their killing and related operations”*

Indicator: an occurrence, observation, record or measurement which has a proven relationship with the legal requirement, which can be:

- **Animal-based indicator (ABI):** a response of an animal or an effect on an animal used to assess its welfare. It can be taken directly on the animal or indirectly and includes the use of animal records.

Example: Wing flapping as ABI of consciousness.

- **Resource-based indicator (RBI):** an evaluation of a feature of the environment in which the animal is kept or to which it is exposed.

Example: Frequency, minimum average current (mA/bird) and duration of exposure to the waterbath.

- **Management-based indicator (MBI):** an evaluation of what the animal unit manager or stockperson does, and which management processes or tools are used.

Example: Presence of standard operating procedures.

Area of concern: the difficulties of an indicator to be used or implemented.

Example: problem with validity, repeatability or feasibility.

Gap of knowledge: lack of technical and scientific information about the indicators.

Example: The large differences of THI values obtained from different equations evidence the limitations of using THI as the unique indicator of thermal stress. Moreover, THI does not take into account the ventilation level, the genotype, age or stocking density.

2. Methodology

The European Union (EU) legislation related to the three priority areas: protection of chickens kept for meat production¹, protection of laying hens² and welfare at the time of killing³ was examined for the identification of the legal requirements related to the three priority areas. Only those requirements related to broiler welfare on farm, laying hens in alternative housing systems and assessment of the state of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys were kept to be included in this deliverable.

Once this set of requirements was selected, specific indicators for animal welfare assessment were listed and accordingly split into the aforementioned categories (*i.e.*, ABIs, RBIs and MBIs). These indicators were retrieved from both literature review and the expertise of the Reference Centre members. However, some legal requirements could not be associated to any clear specific indicator. Thus, area of concern and gap of knowledge related to the indicators were described and selected for a future discussion with the Competent Authorities (CA) of EU member states. For that purpose, the Reference Centre for animal welfare for poultry and other small farmed animals has been presented to the CAs, and national legislations were requested along with the checklists used and the guidelines of the indicators related to the three priority areas. In this deliverable, only the documentation of the four EU member states that belong to the Consortium (*i.e.*, France, Spain, Italy and Denmark) were examined.

Combining the first approach of the indicator list obtained by literature review and expertise with the one obtained by the documentation provided from the four CAs, a final list of the existing welfare indicators was obtained and reported in the present deliverable. The methodology is summarised in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1. Methodology of sub-activity 2.1.

¹ Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes and Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007 laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

² Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes and Council Directive 1999/74/EC of 19 July 1999 laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens.

³ Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing.

3. Relevant welfare indicators of the state of consciousness after waterbath stunning in broilers and turkeys

3.1. Legal requirement: *“Animals shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress or suffering during their killing and related operations”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 3, Paragraph 1)

3.1.1. ABIs:

Associated with pre-stun shocks at the entrance of the waterbath (EFSA, 2019):

- Vigorous wing flapping.
- Withdrawal reactions of wings or head.
- Vocalizations.

Associated with delayed loss of consciousness after immersion of the head:

- Wing flapping while the head of the birds is immersed in the waterbath and before tonic seizure occurs.

3.1.2. RBIs:

Associated with pre-stun shocks:

- Design, construction and maintenance of the ramp: steeply inclined and electrically isolated, ascending over the entrance to the waterbath and it should prevent the flow of water running onto it from the waterbath.
- Design, construction and maintenance of the shackle line: absence of curves before the entrance of the waterbath as it may cause wing flapping and, therefore, increase probability of pre-stun shocks.

Associated with delayed loss of consciousness after immersion of the head:

- Frequency, minimum average current (mA/bird) and duration of exposure to the waterbath stunning according to the regulation (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3)

Area of concern: although waterbath stunning is carried out with the minimum currents stated in the law, under-sized birds might miss the stunner and over-sized birds may not be properly stunned (EFSA, 2019). It can be avoided by not hanging neither under nor over-sized animals on the shackle line with the other birds, but keeping them back and treating them separately accordingly to their size. On the other hand, it is difficult to assess that birds are exposed to the current for at least four seconds due to lack of visibility.

3.1.3. MBIs:

Associated with the state of consciousness:

- Records of frequency of calibration and maintenance of the equipment. It should be according to the manufacturer specifications.
- Presence of certificate of competence and staff training.
- Standard operating procedures (SOP) of the monitoring of stun effectiveness.

3.2. Legal requirement: “The loss of consciousness and sensibility shall be maintained until the death of the animal” (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 4, Paragraph 1)

3.2.1. ABIs:

- **State of consciousness:** EFSA (2013a) recommends that all birds must be checked for the state of consciousness at two key stages: (1) between the exit from the waterbath and neck cutting and (2) during bleeding, with a minimum of two indicators of consciousness per key stage checked simultaneously on each observed animal. The animal is considered conscious when at least one of the indicators is present. ABIs presented in this deliverable are based on feasibility, sensibility and specificity of the indicators assessed by EFSA (2013a).

- Key Stage 1: The recommended indicators of the state of consciousness are:

- Tonic seizures: effective electrical stunning leads to onset of tonic seizure. The tonic seizure as seen in stunned, shackled birds can be recognised from the occurrence of an arched and stiff neck (*i.e.* necks appear parallel to the ground in birds hanging from the shackle line) and wings held tightly close to the body.
- Breathing: effective electrical stunning will lead to immediate onset of apnoea (*i.e.*, absence of breathing). Ineffective electrical stunning can be recognised from the sustained/presence of breathing, including laboured breathing).
- Spontaneous blinking. It is expected only in conscious birds and can be used as an indicator in all key stages of monitoring. However, not all the conscious birds will show spontaneous blinking, and hence absence of blinking does not always mean that the bird is unconscious. Since unconscious birds will not show blinking, this indicator is not applicable to monitoring unconsciousness.

Additional indicators are:

- Corneal or palpebral reflex. Effective electrical stunning will lead to abolition of corneal reflex. Effectively stunned and neck-cut birds show no corneal reflex during any key stage. On the other hand, ineffectively or poorly stunned birds and those recovering consciousness prior to sticking or during bleeding are expected to show a positive corneal reflex at any key stage.
- Vocalisations: is expected only in conscious birds and can be used as an indicator in all key stages of monitoring. However, not all conscious birds will vocalise, and hence absence of vocalisation does not always mean that the bird is unconscious. Birds showing vocalisation must be re-stunned. Since unconscious birds will not vocalise, this indicator is not applicable to monitoring unconsciousness.

- Key Stage 2: recommended indicators are:

- Wing flapping: is expected only in conscious birds and can be used as an indicator at all key stages of monitoring. However, not all the conscious birds will show wing flapping, and hence absence of wing flapping does not always mean that the bird is unconscious. Birds showing wing flapping must be re-stunned. Since unconscious birds will not show wing flapping, this indicator is not applicable to monitoring unconsciousness.
- Breathing.

Additional indicators are:

- Corneal or palpebral reflex
- Spontaneous swallowing (deglutition reflex) of blood entering the mouth during bleeding has been reported in the majority of the birds that have been ineffectively stunned.

- Head shaking. Head shaking during bleeding (probably triggered by the entry of blood into nostrils) has been reported in majority of the birds that have been ineffectively stunned.

NOTE: EFSA (2013a) recommends assessing the bird's consciousness by using a minimum of two indicators per key stage and checked simultaneously on each animal.

- Electroencephalograms (EEG).

Area of concern: not feasible for official controls yet.

3.2.2. RBIs:

- Frequency, minimum average current per animal and duration of the immersion of the bird's head into the water at stunning as stated in **Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3.**

Area of concern: Birds electrically immobilised but conscious due to the use of inappropriate electrical parameters may resemble effectively stunned birds because muscle function is inhibited, and physical reflexes are suppressed. Therefore, the previous ABIs are not reliable. It is difficult to distinguish between a non-effective stunned bird (*i.e.*, paralysed but conscious) from an effective stunned bird (*i.e.*, unconscious) using ABIs as stated by HSA (2015). In order to avoid non-effective stunned birds, compliance of the electrical parameters described at **Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3** is fundamental.

The higher the slaughter speed and the lower the space between animals is the more difficult it is to assess the consciousness of the birds (EFSA, 2019).

3.2.3. MBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility in birds between the end of the stunning process and death.

- Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff correctly assess the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death as it is planned in the SOP in a representative sample of birds.

Frequency of staff shifts for fatigue avoidance.

3.3. Legal requirement: *"The waterbath shall be designed in such a way that the level of immersion of the birds can be easily adapted"* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.6.)

3.3.1. ABIs: None.

3.3.2. RBIs:

- Adequate waterbath height and water level.
- Visually inspection of full submersion of all birds' head in the batch, including the eyes and the cranium (HSA, 2015).

3.3.3. MBI:

- SOP about the abattoir personnel checking and adjusting if necessary, the height of the waterbath and the water level to allow full submersion of the bird's head, including the eyes and cranium of all birds in the batch (HSA, 2015).

3.4. Legal requirement. *“The electrodes in waterbath stunning equipment shall extend the full length of the waterbath. The waterbath shall be designed and maintained in such a way that when the shackles pass over the water they are in continuous contact with the earthed rubbing bar”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.7.)

3.4.1. ABIs: None.

3.4.2. RBIs: Visual inspection

- Length of the electrode placed in the water with an extension of the full length of the waterbath.
- Continuous contact with the earthed rubbing bar.

3.4.3. MBIs: None.

3.5. Legal requirement. *“The whole length of the shackle line up to the point of entry into the scald tank shall be easily accessible in case animals have to be removed from the slaughter line”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.3.)

3.5.1. ABIs: None.

3.5.2. RBIs:

- Assessment of the design, construction and maintenance of the shackle line to allow personnel safely and easily assess and access birds quickly in emergencies at any point on a shackle line, from shackling to entry to a scald tank.

3.5.3. MBIs: None.

3.6. Legal requirement. *“Access to the waterbath stunning equipment shall be available to allow the bleeding of birds that have been stunned and remain in the waterbath as a result of a breakdown or delay in the line”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.9.)

3.6.1. ABIs: None.

3.6.2. RBIs:

- Design, construction and maintenance of the waterbath to allow personnel safely and easily access birds.

3.6.3. MBIs: None.

3.7. Legal requirement. *“Waterbath stunning equipment shall be fitted with a device which displays and records the details of the electrical key parameters used. These records shall be kept for at least one year.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Annex II, Point 5.10.)

3.7.1. ABIs: None.

3.7.2. RBIs: None.

3.7.3. MBIs:

-Presence of a device that displays and records the details of the electrical key parameters used and regularly calibrated.

3.8. Legal requirement. *“Business operators shall ensure that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff carry out regular checks to ensure that the animals do not present any signs of consciousness or sensibility in the period between the end of the stunning process and death.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 1)

3.8.1. ABIs: None.

3.8.2. RBIs:

- Presence of SOP related to the assessment of consciousness or sensibility in birds between the end of the stunning process and death.

3.8.3. MBIs:

- Check that persons responsible for stunning or other nominated staff assess correctly the consciousness and sensibility of birds between the end of the stunning process and death as it is planned in the SOP in a representative sample of birds.

Area of concern: The higher the slaughter speed and the lower the space between animals, the more difficult it is to assess the consciousness of the birds (EFSA, 2019).

3.9. Legal requirement. *“Those checks shall be carried out on a sufficiently representative sample of animals and their frequency shall be established taking into account the outcome of previous checks and any factors which may affect the efficiency of the stunning process.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 2)

3.9.1. ABIs: None.

3.9.2. RBIs:

- The personnel assess the consciousness and sensibility with the appropriate frequency on a representative sample of birds.

- Calculation of a representative sample of birds based on the methodology published by EFSA (2013b)

Area of concern: The higher the slaughter speed and the lower the space between animals, the more difficult it is to assess the consciousness of the birds (EFSA, 2019). So far, there is a lack for sampling protocol to evaluate stunning efficiency at slaughterhouse.

3.9.3. MBIs: None.

3.10. Legal requirement. *“When the outcome of the checks indicates that an animal is not properly stunned, the person in charge of stunning shall immediately take the appropriate measures as specified in the standard operating procedures drawn up in accordance with Article 6(2)”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 5, Paragraph 3.)

3.10.1. ABIs:

- Consciousness and sensibility before and after re-stunning of birds using at least two ABIs described and related to **Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, 4, Paragraph 1.**

3.10.2. RBIs:

- Presence or absence of back-up stunning methods in sufficient number.

3.10.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP.
- Record of re-stunned birds.

3.11. Legal requirement. *“Business operators shall ensure that (...) slaughter operations (...) are only carried out by persons holding a certificate of competence for such operations (...), demonstrating their ability to carry them out in accordance with the rules laid down in this Regulation.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 7)

3.11.1. ABIs: None.

3.11.2. RBIs:

- Staff with certificate of competence delivered by the corresponding EU member state.

3.11.3. MBIs: None.

3.12. Legal requirement. *“(...) The checks (...) shall include (...) indicators designed to detect signs of unconsciousness and consciousness or sensibility in the animals; indicators designed to detect the absence of signs of life in the animals slaughtered (...) in accordance with Article 4(4); criteria for determining whether the results shown by the indicators referred to in point (b) are satisfactory; the circumstances and/or the time when the monitoring must take place; the number of animals in each sample to be checked during the monitoring; appropriate procedures to ensure that in the event that the criteria referred to in point (c) are not met, the stunning or killing operations are reviewed in order to identify the causes of any shortcomings and the necessary changes to be made to those operations.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 2.)

3.12.1. ABIs: None.

3.12.2. RBIs: None

3.12.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP that includes a control procedure of stunning. Check non-conformities and that remedial actions are well listed and relevant.

3.13. Legal requirement. *“Business operators shall put in place a specific monitoring procedure for each slaughter line.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 3)

3.13.1. ABIs: None.

3.13.2. RBI: None.

3.13.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of SOP that indicate setting and using characteristics of slaughter equipment, a procedure to assess animal's death to guarantee animals are dead before further dressing or scalding.
- Check non-conformities and that remedial actions are well listed and relevant.

3.14. Legal requirement. *“The frequency of the checks shall take into account the main risk factors, such as changes regarding the types or the size of animals slaughtered or personnel working patterns and shall be established so as to ensure results with a high level of confidence.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 4)

3.14.1. ABIs: None.

3.14.2. RBIs: None.

3.14.3. MBIs:

- Frequency of the checks.

Gap of knowledge: The optimal frequency depends on several factors and may vary among slaughterhouses. In this sense, the animal welfare officer should periodically sample the slaughter population and the sampling fraction can be calculated using the statistical model proposed by EFSA (2013b). This fraction is dependent on the test sensitivity, the slaughtered population, the maximum allowed threshold failure rate and the required accuracy (EFSA, 2013a).

3.15. Legal requirement. *“For the purpose of paragraphs 1 to 4 of this Article 16, business operators may use monitoring procedures as described in the guides to good practice referred to in Article 13. Community guidelines concerning monitoring procedures in slaughterhouses may be adopted in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 25(2).”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 16, Paragraph 5 and 6)

3.15.1. ABIs: None.

3.15.2. RBIs:

- Presence or absence of monitoring procedures as described in the guides to good practice.

3.15.3. MBIs:

- Check the use of these monitoring procedures.

3.16. Legal requirement. *“Member States shall encourage the development and dissemination of guides to good practice to facilitate the implementation of this Regulation.”* (Council Regulation (EC) 1099/2009, Chapter II, Article 13, Paragraph 1)

3.16.1. ABIs: None.

3.16.2. RBIs: None.

3.16.3. MBIs:

- Presence or absence of guides to good practice.

- Dissemination of the information related to guides to good practice.

4. Conclusions

Conclusions specific to Priority 3 - State of consciousness after waterbath stunning of broilers and turkeys:

- 1) A total of 16 legal requirements regarding the assessment of the state of consciousness have been identified in the Council Regulation 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing.
- 2) Hence, only 5 of these requirements can be evaluated using ABIs. Therefore, most legal requirements are assessed by using RBIs and/or MBIs.
- 3) The state of consciousness is assessed in two key stages 1) between the exit from the waterbath stunning to neck cutting and 2) during bleeding. A minimum of two indicators should be used in each key stage.
- 4) The higher the line speed and the lower the distance between birds, the more difficult it is for the inspector to assess the ABIs state of consciousness in all birds. Thus, there is a need for assessing which ABIs are more valid, reliable and feasible at high-speed slaughtering, and/or short distance between birds in the line.
- 5) When the electrical parameters of the waterbath stunning are not the appropriate, birds can be evaluated as unconscious when actually conscious but electro-immobilised. In this sense, there is no ABI that could discern between conscious and paralysed birds and the RBI rise as crucial to follow the frequency, minimum average current per animal and duration of the immersion of the bird's head into the water at stunning as stated in Annex I, Chapter II, Point 6.3.

5. References

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